

Open channel model using a coupled MASCARET-MATLAB Model

Matthieu Breysse
 Hydraulic Engineering Center
 EDF
 La Motte Servolex, France
matthieu.breysse@edf.fr

Abstract — In studies performed by EDF's Hydro Engineering Centre, MASCARET software is widely used to model channels with associated dams and power plants.

This paper presents MASCARET simulations made to estimate the impact of a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) dysfunction on the water level in the channels.

When the PLC that governs the level and flow regulation on the dam is not working, different scenarios are simulate with Mascaret to estimate where and when the water level will reach the top of the side embankments of the open-channels upstream of the dam.

This paper presents:

- MASCARET model used
- Power plants and dams characteristics
- MASCARET simulations with PLC dysfunction
- MASCARET MATLAB simulations with PLC dysfunction and additional safety PLC installed
- TELEMAC-2D simulation

I. MASCARET MODEL

Fudaa-Mascaret version : 3.6

Code : Mascaret 8.1

Unsteady subcritical flow calculation

Fig. 1 Mascaret Model

Boundaries conditions used:

- 3 hygrograms for the 2 power plants and the upstream dam.
- Weir defined low $Q = f(Z_{\text{upstream}})$ for the downstream dam [1]

The time step is constant and is equal to 2 s.

The mesh is discretized with a size of 20 m along the 20 km of channels.

The blue arrows on the figure 1 represents the navigation locks.

II. DOWNSTREAM POWER PLANT AND DAM

Downstream power plant has 4 turbines and a design flow of 1680 m³/s. In case of turbines triggering, 4 turbine bypass can evacuate 1280 m³/s.

Downstream dam is a 178 m long and 5 open gate-structure dam. Each of the 5 sluices is equipped with 2 fixed wheel gates:

- Overtopping superior gate
- Rising inferior gate

Each of the 5 sluices can spill up to 1200 m³/s

The downstream dam have a new PLC and the MASCARET simulations will be used to estimate PLC dysfunction consequences.

III. MASCARET SCENARIOS WITH DOWNSTREAM DAM PLC DYSFUNCTION

5 scenarios with PLC dysfunction are simulated:

- Scenario 1 : 2 cumulated disorders
Constant flood gradient of the upstream dam
Downstream dam's PLC out of order with all gates closed
- Scenario 2 : 3 cumulated disorders
Downstream power plant flow from 1680 m³/s to 0 m³/s: 4 turbines triggered and turbines bypass out of order
Downstream dam's PLC out of order with all gates closed
- Scenario 3 : 3 cumulated disorders
Downstream power plant flow from 1280 m³/s to 960 m³/s: 4 turbines triggered and turbines bypass partially working
Downstream dam's PLC out of order with all gates closed
- Scenario 4 : 3 cumulated disorders
Downstream power plant flow from 1680 m³/s to 960 m³/s: 4 turbines triggered and turbines bypass partially working
Downstream dam's PLC out of order with gates opened with 2640 m³/s outflow
- Scenario 5 : 2 cumulated disorders
Inadvertent opening of the upstream dam
Downstream dam's PLC out of order with all gates closed

For the 5 scenarios, water flow lines are computed on the 5 channels of the model.

The computation is ended when the water level reach the crest of the side embankment.

As a conservative approach, the calculated values are increased to incorporate uncertainties.

- Water raise compare to initial water flow lines are increased by 10%
- Duration before the water level reach the crest of the side embankment is reduced by 13%

As the scenario computed cannot be tested for real onsite, this method affords a greater level of protection.

Below is an example of result for the 4th scenario; the increased water flow line reach the crest of the side embankment in the headrace canal of the downstream power plant.

Fig. 3 Result for the 4th scenario
Based on the increased flow line at 1h25m, the time evolution of the water level at the first location where the water will reach the crest is as following:

Fig. 4 Time evolution for the 4th scenario

The reduction of 13% of the duration suggest a potential reach of the side embankment crest after 1h15m.

The 5 scenarios allow to estimate the risk associated with the downstream dam PLC dysfunction (where and when the water level will reach the side embankment).

For scenarios associated with PLC error, FUDAA-MASCARET simulations showed a risk of spill along the side dams of the open-channel upstream of the dam.

Based on MASCARET results; to avoid spills and to strengthen the safety, EDF decided to install a safety PLC in association with the new regular PLC of the downstream dam.

The 5 scenarios are replayed with the simulation of the safety PLC.

IV. MASCARET SCENARIOS WITH DOWNSTREAM DAM PLC DYSFUNCTION AND SAFETY PLC MODELED

The safety PLC is activated by floating switches when water level is higher than regular water level at the downstream dam. The safety PLC will maneuver the gates to stop the water level rising.

The safety PLC:

- Is activates when the float switch level sensor detect the rising level
- Commands the gates maneuvers
- Is deactivated when the float switch level sensor detect the lowering level

Safety PLC modelling in MASCARET need a complex boundary condition for the downstream dam. Indeed the downstream dam flow will vary with:

- Gates positions
- Upstream water level
- Downstream water level (downstream level can lower the theoretical gates flows)

3 options have been considered to model the scenarios with safety PLC operating the gates:

- A) MASCARET solution with the use of the boundary condition « Gate opening Z_{inf} , $Z_{sup} = f(t)$ [2]
- B) Call MASCARET API with Python script
- C) Call MASCARET API with Leg'Eau

A) The boundary condition « Gate opening Z_{inf} , $Z_{sup} = f(t)$ [2] is supposed to simulate a gate maneuvers. This condition has never been used in EDF Hydro studies and cannot model the complexity of the flow calculation.

Fig. 5 Boundary condition Gate opening Z_{inf} , Z_{sup}

- B) Call MASCARET API with Python script that will calculate a new Weir defined low $Q = f(Z_{upstream})$ at each time step.
- C) In association with EDF R&D, a MATLAB overlay called LEG'EAU has been built and used for several years by EDF Hydro engineers. This overlay, can do the pre and post-processing and can simulate the operation and the PLC of all boundaries of the model.

For this study, LEG'EAU was used to simulate a MASCARET model with variable boundary condition at the downstream dam ; when the safety PLC is activated, a new boundary condition is calculated with MATLAB for every time step.

This MATLAB MASCARET model was used to determine:

- Height of the switch level sensor that will active the safety PLC
- Safety PLC routine to command the gates maneuvers and to prevent any water level rising

V. TELEMAC 2D MODEL TO DETERMINE THE POSITION OF SWITCH LEVEL SENSORS

Additionally to 1D simulation, a TELEMAC 2D model was used to determine the position of switch level sensors that will activate safety PLC of the downstream dam.

Fig. 6 Telemac 2D result

The figure 6 shows the free surface with a flow of $6000 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ through the 5 opened sluices of the dam.

As showed on the figure bellow, important level variation can appears between right and left bank of the dam:

Fig. 7 TELEMAC 2D cross section result at the downstream dam

This figure shows that for high flow with the 5 sluices of the dam opened, the main flow is located on the left bank, where there is a strong lowering of the free surface.

To avoid being sensitive to the local drops of water, it was chosen to implant the switch level sensors on the beginning of the right bank at the headrace canal.

VI. CONCLUSION

MASCARET software allow to represent great lengths (20 km of channels) and simple boundaries conditions.

When a PLC needs to be model, MASCARET has no native solution to do so and a MATLAB MASCARET was used to simulate safety PLC.

To parameter the safety PLC using MATLAB MASCARET results, a fruitful collaboration between hydraulic and control-command engineers is needed.

To strengthen the methodology of the evaluation of a PLC dysfunction, it would be also important to evaluate the probability of the studied scenarios.

REFERENCE

- [1] Mascaret v8.0 Application guide Copyright 2014 EDF – CEREMA
- [2] Guide de prise en main Fudaa Mascaret 3.0 – Notice GT 08.01 Avril 2008